

CELLULOSE WHISKERS AND POLY(BUTYL ACRYLATE STYRENE) LATEX BASED NANOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS : PERCOLATION EFFECT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Véronique Favier¹, Jean Yves Cavaillé¹, Alain Dufresne¹, Gilles Canova², Stéphane Favier^{2,3},
Suresh Shrivastava³

1/ CERMAV-CNRS, Université J.Fourier, BP 53X, F-38041 Grenoble Cedex 9

2/ GPM2, ENSPG, UA CNRS, BP 46, F-38402 St Martin d'Hères Cedex

3/ Department of Civil Engineering and Applied Mechanics, McGill University, 817 Sherbrooke Street West, Montreal, QC, Canada

ABSTRACT

Nanocomposites materials were processed by casting a mixture of a latex and an aqueous suspension of cellulose whiskers. It has been found that the mechanical properties (shear modulus) are increased by more than three orders of magnitude in the rubbery state of the polymer matrix, when the whisker content is 6%(w/w). This very large and unusual effect is discussed on the basis of different types of mechanical models and it is concluded that these whiskers form a rigid network linked by hydrogen bonds. The formation of this network is assumed to be governed by a percolation mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Native cellulose as fiber or short-fibers forms have widely displayed their potential for the reinforcement of elastomeric or thermoplastic polymers [1-4]. These macroscopic reinforcing agents are actually themselves composite structures hiding a great number of intermediate level of organization. They occur as whisker-like microfibrils that are bio-synthesized and spun in a continuous fashion. Each microfibril can therefore be considered as a true polymer whisker having mechanical properties close to those of cellulose crystals. These elementary units, such as microfibrils and microcrystals, appear as a new potential as reinforcing agents still little exploited [2]. In this work, cellulose whiskers extracted from the mantles of tunicates (sea-food animals) were mixed homogeneously into synthetic polymer latices. Casting these mixtures leads to the formation of a cellulose whisker network increasing drastically the mechanical properties of the composite even with a whisker weight fraction as low as a few percent. Classical models for short fiber composites have then no more applicability and percolation effect must be taken into account.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

PREPARATION OF THE MATERIALS

Cellulose whiskers were extracted from tunicates (sea-food animals found in Japanese and Mediterranean seas). Mantle of tunicates are made of cellulosic microfibrils particularly well organized and crystallized, which lead, after acid hydrolysis, to microcrystals (whiskers) with lengths ranging from 0.1 μm to several μm , and widths of 10 to 20 nm. Their aspect ratio can be greater than 100 (Figure 1). In water, whiskers are stabilized by sulfate groups, resulting in colloidal aqueous suspension.

A latex resulting from the emulsion copolymerization of styrene (35%(w/w)) and butyl acrylate (65%(w/w)) monomers was supplied by Atochem, Serquigny, France. The aqueous dispersion contained spherical particles of 150 nm average diameter and had a 50% (w/w) solid fraction (Figure 1). The glass-rubber transition temperature (T_g) of the copolymer was equal to 0°C.

Mixtures of this latex and tunicin whiskers were prepared to produce composites having a weight fractions of cellulose ranging from 0% to 14%. Solid composite films were processed by casting at 30°C.

Figure 1. 1A : Transmission electron micrograph (TEM) of a typical preparation of tunicin crystals (whiskers). Insert : Electron diffraction diagram recorded on an area of a crystal ; the direction c^* corresponds to the cellulose chain axis. 1B : TEM of the latices. Scale bar : 0.5 μm

DYNAMIC MECHANICAL MEASUREMENTS

Figure 2 shows the plot of the shear modulus, G , as a function of temperature for composites filled with various amounts of tunicin whiskers. The curve corresponding to the pure matrix is typical of a thermoplastic behavior : for temperatures below the glass-rubber transition temperature, T_g , the copolymer is in the glassy state and G remains about constant (around 1 GPa) ; then, a rapid and intense decrease in the elastic shear modulus, by more than four decades, is observed, corresponding to the glass-rubber transition ; in the terminal zone, G becomes lower and lower ($<0.1\text{MPa}$) with increasing temperature . When reinforced by a small percentage of tunicin whiskers, the polymer films show increased mechanical properties, this increase being particularly striking when the films are heated above the glass transition of the matrix. The magnitude of the G -drop occurring in the glass transition region becomes extremely small when 6% cellulose whiskers are added, going from 1 GPa to only 0.1 GPa. Furthermore, the modulus remains remarkably constant up to 500 K, i.e. the temperature of cellulose degradation.

Figure 2. Log of the shear modulus as a function of temperature. 2A. Reinforcing effect. 2B. Improvement of the thermal stability of the matrix

DISCUSSION

In order to understand the unusual reinforcing effect observed at $T > T_g$ at such a low cellulose concentrations, comparisons between experimental results and different mechanical approaches were made.

MEAN FIELD APPROACH

The theoretical model of Halpin-Kardos gives the elastic shear modulus G_c of short fibers composites [5]. In this approach, fibers are supposed to be dispersed in a continuous matrix and no interaction between fillers is taken into account. The properties of the composite depend on the size, the shape and volume fraction of the fillers and on the mechanical properties of both the matrix and the fibers. The composite is considered to be equivalent to a "quasi isotropic" material made of four layers of oriented plies (at $0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, -45^\circ$) (Fig. 3)

Figure 3. Diagram of a "quasi isotropic" composite

PERCOLATION APPROACH

A first numerical calculation has been performed to determine the threshold fraction (X_c) to reach percolation of the whiskers. For a random distribution of the whiskers, it was found close to 1% (v/v) [6].

Ouali *et al* [7] have adapted the classical series-parallel model, as derived by Takayanagi [8], with the percolation concept (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Diagram of the series-parallel model

The elastic shear modulus G_c of the composite is given by the following equation :

$$G_c = \frac{(1 - 2\psi + \psi X_r) G_s G_r + (1 - X_r) \psi G_r^2}{(1 - X_r) G_r + (X_r - \psi) G_s} \tag{1}$$

The subscripts s and r, refer to the soft and rigid phase, respectively. X is the volume fraction and G the shear modulus. As ψ corresponds to the volume fraction of the percolating rigid phase, it can be calculated, as follows (Eqn.2), with a simple prediction based on the percolation concept [7] :

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= 0 & X_r < X_c \\ \psi &= X_r \left(\frac{X_r - X_c}{1 - X_c} \right)^b & X_r \geq X_c \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where b is the percolation exponent, equal to 0.4 in a 3D analysis [9,10].

In this model, the stiffness of the system is mainly due to infinite aggregates of tunicin whiskers. The rigidity of the network of cellulose crystallites, different of the one of an isolated whisker, is probably due to hydrogen bonds, as it is the case in paper sheets [11]. It is therefore reasonable to estimate the shear modulus of the network as the one of a film made only of cellulose whiskers. This elastic shear modulus was experimentally measured and found equal to 5 GPa (which is very close to the value found by Yamanaka and al [12] for sheets prepared from bacterial cellulose).

Figure 5. Log of the shear modulus, taken at 325 K, as a function of the volume fraction of cellulose whiskers. Comparisons between the experimental data (black dots) and data calculated with two different mechanical approaches : a mean field approach (dashed line) and a percolation approach (continuous line)

The variation of the shear modulus G_c , taken at 325 K (i.e. 50 degrees above T_g) as a function of the whisker content is plotted in Figure 5. G_c calculated by a mean field approach (dashed line) does not fit at all the experimental data, whereas G_c estimated by the percolation approach (solid line) is in good agreement with the mechanical measurements. Above the percolation threshold, a strong increase of the modulus is observed. Therefore, the great reinforcement obtained is not only due to geometric (high aspect ratio) and stiffness (high modulus) properties of tunicin whiskers. Above all, it is ascribed to a percolation effect and to the presence of strong interactions (such as hydrogen bonds) between cellulose whiskers. Casting process leads to the formation of a percolating network of whiskers inside the matrix that strengthens the composite material.

FINITE ELEMENTS METHOD

To better understand what we called a mechanical percolation effect (i.e. a strong change in the mechanical properties at the percolation threshold), we have tentatively modeled the mechanical behavior of the composite studied by a finite element approach. As mentioned before, homogenization schemes (self consistent schemes) are not adequate because actually only applicable to dilute random system. On the other hand, modeling based on regular (periodic) network does not allow to study the mechanical percolation effect namely the evolution of the modulus around the percolation threshold. Finite elements (FE) methods are the easiest way to simulate composites based on a random percolating structure even if making meshes for such systems is difficult to realize automatically. This is the reason why, 2D handmade meshes were created (Figure 6). The whisker area fractions were ranging from 0.9% to 9.5%, the percolation threshold being between 2.6% and 4.8%.

Figure 6. FE mesh corresponding to an area fraction of whiskers equals to 7.3%. Dashed lines correspond to the whiskers and continuous lines correspond to the matrix.

Polymer matrix was represented by 3 nodes constant strain triangular elements (eqn). The behavior of the matrix is elastic isotropic with elastic constants given in table 1. Cellulose whiskers were simulated by two kinds of elements : (i) bars (ball-and-socket joints between whiskers) and (ii) Bernouilli's beams (embedded to one another). In both cases, equations giving the normal stress N , the shear stress T and the moment M as a function of inertial moment I , Young Modulus E , elements length L are the following (Eqn.3 and Eqn.4) :

Figure 7. Diagram of a beam

whiskers (bars)

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \frac{ES}{L}(x_2 - x_1) \\
 T &= 0 \\
 M &= 0
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

whiskers (beams) (Fig. 7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \frac{ES}{L}(x_2 - x_1) \\
 T &= \frac{12EI}{L^3}(y_2 - y_1) - \frac{6EI}{L^2}(\theta_2 + \theta_1) \\
 M &= \frac{6EI}{L^2}(y_2 - y_1 - L\theta_2) + \frac{4EI}{L}(\theta_2 - \theta_1)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

The values of the different parameters are given in Table.1

Table 1. Values of the different parameters used in the finite element method.

E : Young modulus, ν : Poisson's ratio, I : Inertial moment

matrix		whiskers	
rigid	soft	bar	beam
E = 2.6 GPa $\nu = 0.3$	E = 3 MPa $\nu = 0.5$	E = 150 GPa	E = 150 GPa I = $510 \cdot 10^{-10} \mu\text{m}^4$

Figure 7. Log of the Young modulus of the composite as a function of the whisker area fraction.
7A : Case of a rigid matrix. 7B : Case of a soft matrix

The evolution of the elastic modulus of the composite materials as a function of the whisker area fractions is plotted in Figure 8. In the case of a rigid matrix, the modulus was found to vary almost linearly with the whisker content. No real significant difference between bars and beams can be observed. In the case of a soft matrix, structures made of beams display a strong increase of the modulus as soon as a percolating network is formed in the composite (around 3%), whereas the modulus of bar structures still vary linearly with whisker content. These results tend to reveal that a cellulose whisker percolating network acts as a beam percolating network. Therefore, links between tunicin whisker seems to be rigid and fixed. This hypothesis is quite realistic because a high number of hydrogen bonds can be formed in a surface area contact (around 100 nm²) between two whiskers preventing them from rotating one to another.

CONCLUSION

New nanocomposite structures, based on a latex and a cellulose whisker suspensions were processed. They displayed superior mechanical properties even with a whisker weight fraction as low as few percents. It is ascribed to a mechanical percolation effect, including the geometric percolation of the fillers and the presence of strong interactions between fillers. These interactions are responsible of the cohesion (solid nodes) and the stiffness (solid links) of the percolating network.

REFERENCES

1. P. Fink and B. Stenberg, Mechanical properties of natural rubber/grafted cellulose fiber composites. *British Polym. J.* **22**, 147-153 (1990)
2. A. Boldizar, C. Klason, P. Näslund and P. Saha, Prehydrolyzed cellulose as reinforcing filler for thermoplastics. *Intern. J. Polymeric Mater.* **11**, 229-262 (1987)
3. R. G. Raj, B. V. Kokta, G. Grouleau and C. Daneault, The influence of coupling agents on mechanical properties of composites containing cellulosic fillers. *Polym. Plast Technol. Eng* **29**, 339-353 (1990)
4. P. Gatenholm, H. Bertilsson and A. Mathiasson, The effect of chemical composition of interphase on dispersion of cellulose fibers in polymers. I. PVC-coated cellulose in polystyrene. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **49**, 197-208 (1993)
5. J. C. Halpin and J. L. Kardos, Moduli of crystalline polymers employing composite theory. *J. Appl. Phys.* **43**, 2235-2241 (1972)
6. V. Favier, J. Y. Cavaillé, H. Chanzy, A. Dufresne and B. Ernst, Nanocomposites with a Polymer Matrix Reinforced by Cellulose Whiskers, *Nanocomposites and Supramolecular Materials Workshop Design, Synthesis and Properties, March 8-11, 1994, San Diego (USA)*
7. N. Ouali, J. Y. Cavaillé, J. Pérez, Elastic, viscoelastic and plastic behavior of multiphase polymer blends, *Plast. Rubber. Comp., Process. Appli.* **16**, 55-60 (1991)
8. M. Takayanagi, S. Uemura and S. Minami, Application of equivalent method dynamic rheo-optical properties of crystalline polymer, *J. Polym. Sci. C* **5**, 113 (1964)
9. D. Stauffer, Introduction to percolation theory. (*Taylor and Francis, London and Philadelphia, 1985*)
10. P. G. De Gennes, Scaling concepts in polymer physics (*Cornell University Press, 1979*)
11. A. H. Nissan, H-Bond Dissociation in Hydrogen Bond Dominated Solids, *Macromolecules* **9**, 840-850 (1976)
12. S. Yamanaka, K. Watanabe, N. Klitamura, M. Iguchi., S. MitsuhashiI, Y. Niski Y., M. Uryu, The Structure and Mechanical Properties of Sheets Prepared from Bacterial Cellulose, *J. Mater. Sci.* **24**, 3141-3145.(1989)